

Demonstration of slicing for PPDR communications

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Abstract—One of the most significant advancements in 5G is the concept of network slice, which allows creating multiple virtual networks on a single physical infrastructure. In the context of mission-critical communications, the usage of end-to-end slices would enable the use of a public 5G network to provide robust, secure, and highly reliable communication systems during Public Protection and Disaster Relief (PPDR) communications. This paper empirically demonstrates the 5G network slices, illustrating their efficacy in supporting differentiated service requirements. We explore the architectural setup, the implementation of slice-specific performance attributes, and the potential impacts on emergency response operations. Our findings aim to contribute to the ongoing discourse on applying 5G technologies for critical communication scenarios, providing insights into the practical challenges and solutions associated with deploying network slices for PPDR purposes.

Keywords—5G, testbeds, slicing, PPDR

I. INTRODUCTION

Network slicing[1] [2] in 5G represents a transformative approach to network usage. Recent research has emphasized network slices' customization and isolation properties, which can be customized to meet the stringent latency, reliability, and security requirements needed for critical applications. Several key developments mark the current landscape of 5G network slicing. Initially, studies focused on the architectural foundations and standardization efforts, predominantly led by organizations such as the Third Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) and the International Telecommunication Union (ITU)[4][3]. These bodies have defined the framework and protocols for implementing network slices, including the management and orchestration layers crucial for dynamic slice deployment and operation. In the domain of PPDR, recent empirical studies have showcased the application of dedicated slices for emergency communications, ensuring prioritized traffic flow and enhanced security measures. These studies highlight the potential of network slices to maintain communication lines during critical incidents, where traditional networks can fail or be overwhelmed.

II. VICTORIA NETWORK

The "Victoria Networks" is a 5G private network operated by the University of Málaga that has been designed to facilitate research and development in 5G network technologies and beyond. This testbed incorporates a comprehensive and scalable architecture that enables extensive testing of 5G features such as slicing and use cases as PPDR. The use cases under test are deployed in a high-performance Kubernetes cluster

that hosts virtualized network functions (VNFs) and serves as the backbone for various network slices. These slices can be customized with specific 5QIs (5G Quality of Service Identifiers) to support different application needs, ranging from high-throughput video streaming services to low-latency communications required by autonomous vehicles or PPDR applications. The private 5G network uses Nokia radio systems and Athonet's 5G core. The network operates on frequency bands n78, n258, and 261.

III. M6 APPLICATION

The Airbus M6 solution is a specialized service designed to provide secure, mission-critical communication solutions. Developed by Airbus Defence and Space, the M6 Client app is tailored for users in public safety, security services, and other sectors that require instant, secure, and reliable communication capabilities. Among the features provided by this application we will focus on the real-time video streaming. This feature enables user sharing live video from their location, enhancing situational awareness for remote teams and command centers. This feature is critical during emergency response operations, where real-time visuals are necessary for effective decision-making.

IV. DEMONSTRATION

This paper demonstrates the application of 5G slicing for preserving the network resources available for PPDR users in network congestion scenarios. As shown in Figure 1 two different end-to-end slices have been configured in the radio and in the 5GCore, one is a default slice for commercial subscribers of the network, the other is the PPDR slice for the PPDR users on the network. In addition, two different UPFs have been configured for each slice. Each slice has half the available bandwidth. The differentiation of the subscribers is done based on the SIM cards. In the default slices there are three user equipments (UEs). The UE 2 is streaming realtime video to the UE 3 while UE1 in the same slice the UE 1 is receiving a intensive data flow that is saturating the network. The incoming data traffic in UE 1 is monitored using the NEMO Handy tool. At the same time, in the PPDR slice, the UE 4 is streaming video to the UE 5. As we can see in Figure 2, the video received by the UE 3 is delayed while the UE 5 is receiving the video without any time deviation. Table I shows the RTT (Round Trip Time) measurements collected by the M6 client during the video streaming, moreover, the application monitors the signal strength and other radio parameters which enables to compare the radio propagation conditions. The radio

Fig. 1. PPDR slicing setup

Fig. 2. PPDR slicing demonstration

measurements are good and very similar, so we can conclude that the radio conditions are not the source of the delays experimented by the UE 3.

Default slice		PPDR slice	
RTT (ms)	Signal Strength (dBm)	RTT (ms)	Signal Strength (dBm)
31	82	16	86
100	82	14	86
51	82	14	85
39	82	16	84
37	82	11	84
35	81	15	84

TABLE I. RTT MEASUREMENTS DURING THE LIVE VIDEO STREAMING SESSION

V. CONCLUSION

The study empirically demonstrates the utility and effectiveness of network slicing in PPDR settings using the Victoria Networks testbed at the University of Málaga. The trials show that slicing can ensure the availability of network resources in congestion scenarios, which is critical for communication in emergency situations. The Victoria Networks testbed serves not only as a platform for validating new 5G technologies and their applications but also as a catalyst for ongoing innovation in next-generation wireless communication. This robust and versatile environment is crucial for advancing knowledge and technology in the telecommunications domain.

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